

ON THE USE OF STUDY DICTIONARIES IN MOTHER LANGUAGE LESSONS OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOLS

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the role, methods and possibilities of using educational vocabulary in the lessons of the native language of secondary school.

To guide students in general secondary education to independent and creative thinking, to introduce them to their national identity, to create a spiritual and educational revolution in their minds, to use Uzbek in various aspects of social, economic and cultural life, in all types of communication and interaction. To be able to use the language easily, freely, effectively, correctly, to enjoy its unlimited possibilities, to acquire the necessary skills related to the secrets of speech etiquette and speech tactics is the responsibility of mother tongue education. After all, the main goal of native language education is to cultivate creative thinkers, to express the product of thinking of each school graduate in his native language in written and oral ways, in accordance with the speech conditions, correctly and fluently, to correctly express the opinions of others. It consists of forming the skills of reception and skills.

1) In the "State educational standards of general secondary education", the purpose of education of the subject "Mother language" was defined as follows in connection with the formation and development of creative thinking: "The main goal of mother tongue education is stands: native language classes should be focused on the formation and development of children's creativity, independent thinking, the ability to correctly and fluently express the product of creative thought in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech conditions. Therefore, the main goal of mother tongue education is to focus on the student's thinking, to sow the seeds of creativity, independent thinking, and to be able to express the product of creative thinking correctly and fluently in oral and written forms in accordance with the speech conditions. As we raise the issue of teaching to learn, we should focus on three aspects of this topic:

1) Teaching the student to be creative and think independently;

- 2) To teach the student to be able to speak correctly, fluently, logically.
- 3) To teach the student to write correctly, fluently, logically.

In order to realize the main goal of mother tongue education, the series of "necessary knowledge to be mastered by 5th grade students" in the "Mother Tongue" program is defined as follows:

The importance of language in the life of a person's society. Uzbek linguistics, Uzbek literary language, Uzbek folk dialects, belonging to the Turkic language family, language and writing, emergence of language, relations between languages, world languages, written literary speech, oral literary speech. Uzbek linguistics: main sections.

Historical and social significance of the law "On State Language".

Syntax. A phrase, a sentence, types of a sentence according to the purpose of expression (declarative sentence, interrogative sentence, imperative sentence, emotion-exciting sentence) are a part of a sentence. The main parts of the sentence: possessive, participle.

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Simple words, simple words, simple words. Secondary parts of the sentence: complement, determiner, case. Punctuation marks, excerpted sentence.

Compound sentences. Don't push.

Phonetics. Correct pronunciation (orpeopia). Graphics, spelling. Parts of speech. Speech sounds and letters, letter combinations. Vowels and consonants. Voiced and unvoiced consonants. The exchange of sounds in words. Spelling of vowels and consonants.

Open and closed joint. Rules of syllable transfer. Dividing the word into syllables. Word stress and logical stress.

Chart: alphabet, word endings, capital letters, hyphens, hyphens, letter combinations, consecutive consonants, basic principles of Uzbek spelling, spelling rules.

Vocabulary of the Uzbek language. The main sources of vocabulary enrichment. Word meaning, dictionary meaning are words with one meaning. The main meaning of the word. The literal and figurative meaning of the word. The use of the word in its own sense as a means of clear and symbolic expression of existence. Synonym (synonym), similar words, antonym (opposite meaning), homonym (similar form) and paronyms. Phrases, their lexical meaning, stylistic place and function in speech.

Explanatory dictionary, spelling dictionary, dictionary of synonyms.

Dictionaries and types of dictionaries.

Spelling dictionary of the Uzbek language. An explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. Dictionary of synonyms of the Uzbek language. Anonymous dictionary of the Uzbek language. Phrases in the Uzbek language.

Morphology. Word composition. Core. Word formation. Constructive base. The root parts of the word. Cognate words. Types of adverbs: word-forming, word-forming, word-changing adverbs.

Criteria for dividing words into categories.

Independent word groups (noun, adjective, number, pronoun, verb, adverb)

Auxiliary word groups (linking, auxiliary, loading, exclamations, modal words, imitative words).

Noun, its dictionary meaning, morphological signs and syntactic function. Meaning types of the noun. Methodical use of nouns. Number forms in nouns. Plural suffix. Variation. Agreements. Possessive suffixes. Structural types of nouns (simple, double, compound and abbreviated nouns).

Verb, its dictionary meaning, morphological signs and syntactic function. Verb to be and without being. Conjugation of the verb. Verb tenses. Past tense, present tense, present-future tense, future tense verbs. Auxiliary verbs.

As can be seen from the above, the 5th grade students are given a basic view of the complex knowledge that children need to learn in secondary general education. However, this does not mean filling students' memory with theoretical knowledge. After all, the DTS requirements in this regard are as follows:

Skills and qualifications that 5th grade students need to acquire: Ability to write words and word forms correctly based on spelling rules.

To be able to explain language units, their important signs, meaning and use.

Learn letters with speech sounds, vowels and consonants, voiced and unvoiced consonants, universal words with limited scope of use, colloquial lexicon with book lexicon, word types and inflections, and possessive words with words. change by adding suffixes, lexical and grammatical meanings of the word, create words with basic words: simple, compound and double words; to be able to distinguish word groups, independent words and auxiliary words, word and word combinations, types of simple sentences, parts of sentences, simple sentences and compound sentences.

Being able to analyze phonetically, lexically, lexically, and morphologically.

To be able to remember a grammatical device and a rule based on a grammatical term, a grammatical term and a rule based on a grammatical device.

Being able to compose a sentence at the level of text creation, to be able to connect independent sentences, to be able to correctly determine the composition of words in a sentence.

To be able to correctly use punctuation marks (in adverbial sentences) in connected clauses, separate comment clauses, imperatives and connecting parts of compound sentences, quotations, dialogues.

Ability to use grammatical terms and concepts, rules and definitions in the process of creating a text. Ability to use different dictionaries. Creating a text that matches the learned sentence constructions.

To be able to read expressively, interrogative, command sentences, connected clauses, separated comment clauses, compound and abstract sentences.

Correct pronunciation of vowels and consonants according to the rules of orthography.

Proper use of synonyms, homonyms, antonyms and similar words in speech, according to the style requirements.

Use of spelling dictionary and bilingual dictionaries, explanatory and other dictionaries.

Being able to give examples of nested words.

To be able to distinguish terms and words specific to the style of words, to be able to tell the semantic differences between them.

According to the requirements of DTS, it is necessary for a 5th grade student to have the ability to "use various dictionaries", i.e. "use spelling dictionaries and bilingual dictionaries, explanatory and other dictionaries" . For this purpose, in every native language class of secondary general education schools, the teacher should form and develop the competence and skills of appropriate and effective use of educational dictionaries in the student, this is native language education. serves as a foundation in ensuring the fulfillment of its purpose.

So, how to use educational dictionaries in 5th grade mother tongue classes?

Usually, our teachers mainly use textbooks in their native language classes. The textbook, based on the curriculum, is the educational material reflecting the educational content, the methods of its acquisition by the student, the analysis considered necessary for the student, the material for generalization, the laws that harmonize the content of the educational materials. includes A textbook is a resource intended for the learner to absorb a certain amount of knowledge, skills, and habits. However, working only with textbooks prevents the formation and development of meaningful creative thinking.

The educational tasks given in the textbook can meet the purpose of education only when they provide directions for the student's independent research, satisfy their constant need for information banks, and encourage creative activity. Therefore, it is necessary not to mix the textbook with the system of tasks that the student is supposed to perform during the lesson and the necessary educational material. By textbook, we mean a set that includes the interpretation of the topic, educational material, exercises, problems, and a system of tasks to be completed by the student. The textbook intended for the formation and development of a real creative thinker should be different from the textbooks available today. So, to achieve the new goal of education, new type of textbooks are needed. In order to form a creative thinker, the educational material should be much wider than textbook materials.

In particular, textbooks in the mother tongue provide students with knowledge and information obtained from various dictionaries (information banks), encyclopedias, reference books, other educational subjects taught at school, and experienced people. To get additional material from (relatives of the students), he can achieve his goal only if he designs a system of creative works on the material not given in the textbook.

The teacher should design the educational process by expanding the educational materials taught in each lesson due to the materials not provided in the textbook. Achieving the new goal of education requires new types of textbooks. With the help of such textbooks, an entrepreneur will be able to develop an active person who has deep knowledge of information sources, who can quickly find the information he needs from it, and who can use it most conveniently for the specific conditions in which he lives. Therefore, new textbooks should not consist of a set of exercises, problems, rules or axioms, but a system of educational tasks.

So, it is known that the demand for educational dictionaries is increasing. Changes in lifestyle and pace of life are first of all reflected in the language. Today, new concepts and names have appeared, the lexicon of our language has been dramatically enriched based on internal and external opportunities; many concepts have become obsolete economically, politically, spiritually and culturally, many words have become obsolete and have become explanatory for today's generation. 15-20 years ago, there was almost no dictionary included in school textbooks. Now, at the end of the textbooks created for each school, lyceum, vocational college, sometimes even at the end of each section, we see dictionaries. This indicates that dictionaries have naturally become a component of education.

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